

Studies on the Nature of Dichloro(dimethylglyoximate)(dimethylglyoxime)cobalt(III) and Mechanism of its Aquation

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Manuscript received 5 September 1975; accepted 29 October 1975.

Experimental evidences have been furnished to indicate that the so-called dichloro(dimethylglyoximate)(dimethylglyoxime)cobalt(III) is indeed dichlorobis(dimethylglyoximate)cobaltic(III) acid. The kinetics of its aquation have been studied conductometrically. Aquations of the complex bound chloride ligands occur in two consecutive steps; at 25° the rate constants for the two steps being, $k_1 = 2.53 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ and $k_2 = 2.08 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$; the corresponding activation parameters are: $\Delta H_1^\ddagger = 16.1 \text{ kcal mole}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_1^\ddagger = -21.4 \text{ e.u.}$; $\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 17.9 \text{ kcal mole}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_2^\ddagger = -20.2 \text{ e.u.}$ It is significant that the aquation of the bisdimethylglyoximate complexes are characterised by relatively lower enthalpy of activation and strongly negative entropy of activation compared to the chloroammine complexes of cobalt(III). The $\Delta S_1^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S_2^\ddagger$ values are indeed comparable to the entropy of hydration of chloride ion, which suggests that aquation occurs by dissociation mechanism in which rupture the Co(III)-Cl bond is virtually complete in the transition state.

IN 1923 Feigl and Rubinstein¹ prepared a dark olive green compound from cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate and dimethylglyoxime in acetone solution, further studied by Thilo² and coworkers, the chemical composition of which corresponds to dichlorobis(dimethylglyoxime)cobalt(II). In 1934, Sen and Rây³ made a detailed study of its chemical properties and found this to be diamagnetic from which they concluded that this green compound is *trans*-dichlorodimethylglyoximate dimethylglyoximecobalt(III). They also observed that the aqueous solution of the substance is strongly acidic with a molar conductivity almost equal to that expected for hydrochloric acid, which they ascribed to the following change in aqueous solution:

where $\text{DmgH}_2 = \text{dimethylglyoxime}$, $\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$.

However, with our present state of knowledge on the aquations of cobalt(III) complexes, the formation of a hydroxo product in acidic solution as envisaged in eqn. (1) seemed unlikely. Moreover, the reaction as represented in eqn. (1) is also expected to proceed slowly and as such this fails to account for the acidity of the aqueous solution unless it has been kept long enough for the reaction to be completed. Detailed studies on the nature of the substance as well as its kinetic behaviour therefore appeared worthy of investigation.

Experimental

Materials

$\text{Co}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)(\text{C}_4\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)\text{Cl}_2$: A pure sample of the compound was prepared from cobalt(II) chloride and dimethylglyoxime (DmgH_2) following the method of Sen and Rây³ and its purity was checked by elemental analysis [Found: Co, 16.29; N, 15.45%. Calcd. for $\text{Co}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)(\text{C}_4\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)\text{Cl}_2$: Co, 16.33; N, 15.52%].

All other chemicals used were of reagent grade.

Distilled water, redistilled in an all-glass still with potassium permanganate and alkali was used for making all the solutions which were stored in Jena glass vessels.

Apparatus

Conductance measurements were made using a Philips conductance bridge (PR 9500/90) and pH values were measured with a precision pH meter, (Radiometer [Denmark], PHM 26).

Nature of $\text{Co}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)(\text{C}_4\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)\text{Cl}_2$:

It has been observed that a freshly prepared aqueous solution (0.001M) of the substance is acidic with a pH of 3.085 (25°) and has a molar conductance of 374 (25°) as against the values of 3.035 and 403 respectively for a solution (0.001M) of hydrochloric acid under the same condition. The conductance of the solution (0.001M) increases and pH decreases slowly with time as indicated below which is accom-

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panied by a colour change from greenish brown to brownish yellow in course of a few hours at 25° :

Time, hr	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Λ_M							
(25°)	374	409	427	441	452	459	463
pH							
(25°)	3.085	3.071	3.060	3.052	3.047	3.043	3.041

Time, hr	24	48	72	144
Λ_M (25°)	494	488	486	471
pH (25°)	3.040	—	3.088	—

The conductance and pH values of the freshly prepared aqueous solution of the green compound indicate that it is a monobasic acid which is practically completely dissociated in aqueous solution and it should therefore be formulated as

The observed changes in conductance and pH of the solution as indicated above further suggests that the following reactions take place in aqueous solution :

The conductance value further indicates that formation of $[\text{Co}(\text{DmgH})_2(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+$ is virtually complete in course of several hours at 25° and the resulting solution contains $[\text{Co}(\text{DmgH})_2(\text{OH}_2)_2]^+$ Cl^- and H^+ ,

Cl^- (the measured values of the molar conductances at 0.001M concentration of $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ and HCl being 101 and 403 respectively at 25°). From the change in conductance and pH values with time it is further to be noted that the diaquo product is stable in solution for at least a day and that decomposition sets in on longer storage; cobalt(II) species has been found to be formed as the final product in the decomposed solution.

Kinetic studies on aquation :

Analysis of the change of conductance with time indicates that the changes expressed in eqn. (2) do occur in two consecutive steps which significantly differ in rate. The first stage reaction leads to a change in conductance owing to conversion of $[\text{Co}(\text{DmgH})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{H}$ into HCl and non-ionic $[\text{Co}(\text{DmgH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$, since the molar conductance of hydrochloric acid is higher than that of $[\text{Co}(\text{DmgH})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{H}$ as mentioned earlier.

For the accurate evaluation of the rate constants of the two steps a procedure was developed based on the following considerations :

Let C_0 , C_t and C_∞ be the conductance values of the solution under identical conditions at '0' time, time 't' and 'infinite' time respectively; then,

$$\alpha C_0 = \Lambda_I T_c \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\alpha C_t = \Lambda_I [\text{I}] + \Lambda_{\text{HCl}} \{[\text{II}] + [\text{III}]\} + \Lambda_{\text{III}} [\text{III}] \quad (4)$$

$$\alpha C_\infty = \Lambda_{\text{HCl}} T_c + \Lambda_{\text{III}} T_c \quad \dots (5)$$

and

$$T_c = [\text{I}] + [\text{II}] + [\text{III}] \quad \dots (6)$$

where α is a constant and is equal to 'cell constant' $\times 10^3$, T_c is equal to the molar concentration

Fig. 1. Evaluation of $(C_\infty - C_t)/t_\infty$ at different temperatures (see text).

of the complex originally taken. [I], [II] and [III] are the molar concentrations of the species $[\text{Co}(\text{DmgH})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{H}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{DmgH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{DmgH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}$ respectively at any stage of the reaction at time (t), while Λ stands for the molar conductance of the species indicated as its subscript at the experimental temperature. Combining the above equations (3)-(6) we get

$$\alpha(C_\infty - C_t) = \Lambda_{III}T_c + \{\Lambda_{HCl} - \Lambda_I\}[I] - \Lambda_{III}[III] \quad (7)$$

At later stages of the reaction $[I] = 0$; hence denoting the value of $(C_\infty - C_t)$ at longer time as $(C_\infty - C_t)'$ we get

$$\alpha(C_\infty - C_t)' = \Lambda_{III}T_c - \Lambda_{III}[III] \quad \dots (8)$$

Since at $t = 0$, $[III] = 0$, the value of $(C_\infty - C_t)'$ extrapolated to t_0 gives $(C_\infty - C_t)'_{t=0}$ (see Fig. 1) and we have

$$\alpha(C_\infty - C_t)'_{t=0} = \Lambda_{III}T_c \quad \dots (9)$$

From equations (7) and (9), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha y &= \alpha\{(C_\infty - C_t) - (C_\infty - C_t)'_{t=0}\} \\ &= \{\Lambda_{HCl} - \Lambda_I\}[I] - \Lambda_{III}[III]. \end{aligned}$$

During initial stages $[III] = 0$;

so, αy (initial stages) = αy_1 (say) = $\{\Lambda_{HCl} - \Lambda_I\}[I]$

or $y_1 \propto [I]$.

For later stages $[I] = 0$;

so, $-\alpha y$ (later stages) = αy_2 (say) = $\Lambda_{III}[III]$

or, $y_2 \propto [III]$

where

$$y_1 = \{(C_\infty - C_t) - (C_\infty - C_t)'_{t=0}\} \quad \text{(at initial stages)}$$

and

$$y_2 = \{(C_\infty - C_t)'_{t=0} - (C_\infty - C_t)\} \quad \text{(at later stages)}.$$

Hence by plotting $\log y_1$ vs. time (t) the rate constant, k_1 , of the first stage reaction is obtained from the slope of the initial linear portion (slope $\times 2.303 = k_1$; see Fig. 2). Similarly by plotting $\log y_2$ vs. t the rate constant, k_2 , of the second stage reaction is obtained from the slope of linear portion at longer time (slope $\times 2.303 = k_2$; see Fig. 3).

Procedure

A solution of the complex was prepared just before carrying out conductance measurement by dissolving requisite quantity (to give a complex concentration of $0.001M$ in the final solution) in water thermostated at the experimental temperature and its volume was immediately made up with thermostated water. A definite volume of this was immediately transferred to the conductivity cell, kept in the thermostat, and the resistance of the solution in the cell was measured immediately and thereafter at suitable time intervals with the cell being kept in the thermostat throughout in the dark. With proper care, the entire process of dissolution

Fig. 2. Evaluation of k_1 .

Fig. 3. Evaluation of k_2 .

of the complex to the first recording of the resistance could be completed within three minutes. The Philips conductance bridge, used for the measurement of conductance, in fact measured the resistance of the solution the reciprocal of which being the conductance which was used in evaluation of the rate constants (see Figs. 2 and 3).

Results and Discussion

The rate constants for the first and second stages of the reaction at different temperatures (25°, 30°, 35° and 40°) are listed in Table I together with the

corresponding $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ values evaluated graphically (Fig. 4) making use of Eyring equation⁴ as usual.

TABLE I

RATE CONSTANTS FOR FIRST (k_1) AND SECOND (k_2) STAGES OF AQUATION AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp., °C	$k_1 \times 10^4$, sec ⁻¹	$k_2 \times 10^5$, sec ⁻¹
25	2.53	2.08
30	3.62	3.43
35	5.53	5.57
40	9.32	9.12
$\Delta H^\ddagger$, k.cal.mole ⁻¹	16.1	17.9
$\Delta S^\ddagger$, e.u.	-21.4	-20.2

Fig. 4. Eyring plots for the evaluation of the activation parameters.

- A: $k = k_1$; B: $k = k_2$;
- h = Planck's constant;
- k = Boltzmann's constant,
- T = Absolute temperature, °K.

A comparison of the kinetic parameters (see Table 2) for the two stages of aquation of dichlorobisdimethylglyoximatocobaltate(III) anion with those of several other chloro complexes of cobalt(III) is interesting.

It is significant that the aquation of the bisdimethylglyoximato complexes are characterised by relatively lower enthalpy of activation and strongly negative entropy of activation compared to the other chloro complexes of cobalt(III) which react at comparable rates. Also, the values of the entropy of activation in the former cases are nearly equal to the entropy of hydration (-22.8 e.u.)⁹ of chloride ion. This suggests that the aquation of these complexes occurs by a dissociative process in which the rupture of the Co-Cl bond is only important and is virtually complete in the transition state. The relatively lower

TABLE 2
KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR AQUATION OF COBALT (III)
COMPLEXES.

Complex	k , sec ⁻¹ (25°)	$\Delta H^\ddagger$, kcal. mole ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$, e.u.	Ref.
Co(NH ₃) ₅ Cl ²⁺	1.67×10^{-6}	24.4	-9	5, 6
Trans-Co(py) ₃ Cl ₂ ⁺	8.17×10^{-6}	—	—	8
Cis-Co(en) ₂ Cl ₂ ⁺	2.5×10^{-4}	21.4	-3	6
Trans-Co(en) ₂ Cl ₂ ⁺	3.17×10^{-5}	26.4	+9	7
Cis-Co(trien)Cl ₂ ⁺	1.5×10^{-4}	—	—	6
Trans-Co(pn) ₂ Cl ₂ ⁺	6.17×10^{-5}	27.4	+14	7
Co(en)(tn)Cl ₂ ⁺	4.33×10^{-4}	26.0	+11	7
Trans-Co(DmgH) ₂ - Cl ₂ ⁻	2.53×10^{-4}	16.1	-21.4	This work
Trans-Co(DmgH) ₂ - (H ₂ O)Cl	2.08×10^{-5}	17.9	-20.2	..

value of enthalpy of activation compared to the other cobalt(III) systems as presented in Table 2 suggests that Co-Cl bond is sufficiently weakened by the dimethylglyoximato ligands. Another but less significant effect may be the overall charge of the complex since the anionic dichloro species has an entropy of activation which is 1.8 kcal/mole lower than that of the non-ionic chloro-aquo species.

It may be mentioned that Várhelyi *et al*¹⁰ have reported the following values for the first stage aquation of Co(DmgH)₂Cl₂⁻ ion which appear grossly incorrect on the basis of the present work : $E_a = 24.1$ kcal mole⁻¹ (i.e., $\Delta H^\ddagger = 23.5$ kcal mole⁻¹); $\Delta S^\ddagger = +5.9$ e.u. They have argued that the positive value of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ indicates a dissociation mechanism. This is however untenable, since in a dissociation mechanism in this case, the solvation of the released chloride ion would lead to a considerable decrease in entropy (-22.8 e.u.) the contribution of which is likely to make the $\Delta S^\ddagger$ considerably negative. It seems that their error in evaluation $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ values is due to an error in the estimate of the rate constant for the release of the first chloride ion due

to their not applying necessary and appropriate correction for the contribution of the consecutive second stage of the aquation leading to the loss of second chloride ion, which as is known from this present work proceeds at a rate only about ten times slower than the rate of release of the first chloride under the experimental conditions. In the present work, the change of conductance with time of the experimental solutions has been analysed properly in a manner that reliable values of both k_1 and k_2 have been obtained and hence the corresponding $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ values are also quite reliable and meaningful for the assignment of the reaction mechanism.

Acknowledgement

These investigations have been carried out with financial assistance from the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi (India); the award of a senior research fellowship to one of us (J.R.) by the said Council is also thankfully acknowledged.

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